

THE IMPACT OF REGIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECTS ON ECONOMIC GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

This thesis examines the impact of regional infrastructure projects on economic growth from both theoretical and practical perspectives. The study analyzes the role of transport, energy, communication, and social infrastructure projects in increasing regional economic activity, attracting investment, expanding employment, and improving production efficiency. In addition, the mechanisms through which infrastructure development reduces interregional economic disparities and promotes sustainable economic growth are substantiated. The results of the thesis have scientific and practical significance for improving regional development policy.

Regional infrastructure projects are one of the important factors ensuring economic growth, which directly affects the production potential, investment attractiveness and economic activity of regions. Investments in the transport, energy, communication and social infrastructure sectors contribute to the structural transformation of the regional economy, market integration and sustainable economic development. In recent years, Uzbekistan has paid great attention to the development of regional infrastructure. According to the results of 2025, the country's gross domestic product grew by 7.7% and amounted to about 1,850 trillion soums. The contribution of investments in transport, construction, energy and service infrastructure to this growth was significant. In particular, in January-September 2025, 443.6 trillion soums were invested in fixed capital, which is an increase of 15.2% compared to the previous year. This confirms the role of infrastructure projects in stimulating economic activity. Transport infrastructure is one of the areas that has the strongest impact on regional economic growth. For example, the reconstruction of the Angren-Pop railway line and major highways has expanded the Fergana Valley's access to domestic and foreign markets. As a result, logistics costs have decreased, the speed of deliveries of industrial enterprises has increased, and the volume of production and investment activity in the region have increased. Such projects serve to strengthen interregional economic ties and reduce disparities between regions. The development of energy infrastructure also makes a significant contribution to economic growth. In recent years, the commissioning of solar and wind power plants in Navoi, Samarkand and Bukhara regions has made it possible to provide industrial enterprises and service sectors with stable energy. This has created the basis for reducing production interruptions, increasing energy efficiency and attracting new investment projects.

The expansion of communication and digital infrastructure is another important factor increasing regional economic activity. The high growth rates of information and

communication services (in the services sector, growth was 8.7 percent, and in information and communication services - more than 20 percent) have a positive impact on the development of small and medium-sized businesses, an increase in the share of e-commerce and digital services. Especially in rural and remote areas, the improvement of Internet infrastructure contributes to the creation of new jobs and an increase in the income of the population. Social infrastructure projects - education, healthcare, housing and communal services - have an indirect but sustainable impact on economic growth. These projects support regional economic development by improving the quality of human capital, increasing labor productivity, and expanding domestic demand. In general, regional infrastructure projects have a direct (investment, production, employment) and indirect (competitiveness, regional integration, human capital) impact on economic growth. Therefore, planning infrastructure projects taking into account the economic characteristics of regions, assessing their effectiveness, and monitoring them are important tasks of regional development policy.

Conclusions and recommendations. The results of the study show that regional infrastructure projects are an important strategic factor in accelerating regional economic growth. Investments in the areas of transport, energy, communications, and social infrastructure serve to increase production capacity, improve the investment climate, expand employment, and strengthen interregional economic integration. The experience of Uzbekistan confirms that the funds invested in infrastructure projects play a significant role in ensuring sustainable growth of gross domestic product. At the same time, the economic efficiency of infrastructure projects directly depends on the quality of their planning, financing and implementation processes. In this regard, it is advisable to select infrastructure projects based on the economic specialization and development potential of the regions, direct investment resources to priority areas, and expand public-private partnerships (PPP). As practical proposals, it is recommended to introduce a system of clear indicators to assess the effectiveness of infrastructure projects, strengthen mechanisms for continuous monitoring and evaluation of projects, as well as give priority to digital and “green” infrastructure projects. These measures will serve to enhance the impact of regional infrastructure projects on economic growth and ensure sustainable regional development.

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